

Applications of the Latin Language in Speech

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Sep 2024; **Published:** 18 Oct 2024

Abstract: This article discusses the use of the original and late Latin. In the Middle Ages, Latin was a means of communication for all educated people in Europe. Latin continued to be an international language in medicine and biology. In many fields of science, primarily zoology and botany, terminology is based on Latin.

Keywords: phonetics, articulation, transcription, Latin, term, biology, medicine, doctor, language, zoology, botany, pharmacy, clinic.

The original Latin, which originated in the Roman Empire and was used as an official language, differs quite significantly from its medieval version. Church Latin, although closer to the original version, was also borrowed in pronunciation. In the Middle Ages, Latin was a means of communication for all educated people in Europe. All scientific texts were written in Latin. During this period, universities were founded in Western Europe, and medicine as one of the sciences could be studied there under the guidance of master doctors. Initially, Latin did not act as a "dead" language. It became such only in the IX century. It was during this historical period that the colloquial form of Latin ceased to enjoy previous popularity among the local population. People in everyday communication began to switch to new languages at that time – such as Italian, French, Spanish, Romanian, etc. Over time, Latin began to disappear from the spoken language of people.

In the XVII-XVIII centuries, Latin continued to be an international language in medicine and biology. In many fields of science, primarily zoology and botany, terminology is based on Latin. For example: Cuculus canorus (cuckoo canoris), Culex (mosquito), Parus (tit), microscopicus (microscopic), bronchioles (bronchiola), histogenesis (histogenesis), phytophagus (plant-eating), Malus (apple tree), reflexus (reflex), Agaricus-Agaricus, alga- algae, albiceps - white-headed, allium- onion; garlic, aloë -aloe, anas-(anas americāna), duck (duck)americana), amygdāla-almond, anophēles malaria - mosquito, apis-bee, aviculā-bird, aviculāris- avian, bacca- berry, baccūla-berry, beta- (Beta perennis), beet - (Beet perennis), bipes-bipedal, bialātus-dipteran, botanīca-botany, brevicaudātus-short-tailed, brevicollis- short-necked, brevilanōsus- short-haired, short-haired, brevirostris short-billed, brevis- short ,campanūla-bell , caper-goat etc.

Despite the fact that Latin is called "dead", its use in the modern world is widespread. It still continues to be an important way of communication in many areas of human activity. For example: student, aviation, bus, administrator, academic, album, ammeter, amplitude, antenna, English, certificate, audio, auction, vaccine, general, generator, grammar, deposit, detective, discussion, doctor, etc.

Latin is traditionally used in medicine, in anatomical, clinical and pharmaceutical terminology. Knowledge of Latin allows doctors from different countries of the world to easily understand each other. The long-standing tradition of using Latin in medicine serves as a unifying factor for physicians around the world and for the unification of medical education. If the words are pronounced in Latin: costa ,

cranium -skull ,scapula-scapula, vertebra – vertebra , os – bone , musculus – muscle, larynx – larynx, cervix - neck, neck cilium – eyelash, cystis – bladder , caput – head , collum – neck, lac – milk ,acidum-acid, articularis- articular, cerebrum-brain,cervix -neck, bacterium-bacterium , cito- quickly, clinica-clinic , cilium-eyelash, cavitas- cavity ,crus-leg,cancer-cancer, coccygeus- coccyx,facies-faces, cellula-cell, incisura- incision, accesorius-accessory ,arcus- bow,processus-process,cystis,-cysts,cysterna-cistern,cylindricus-cylindrical,biceps-biceps, cytologia-cytology,contractura-contraction,centralis-central,cylind-raceus-cylindrical ,medici- doctors ,cytus-cytus , then all doctors understand what it is about.

Many people still continue to use words from Latin, as well as phrases from this language. In the names of diseases, pathological conditions, methods of treatment and examination of the patient, diagnoses and treatments, almost all national languages of clinical medicine use Latin terminology, which can be known as part of any modern "living" language, for example, terms such as bronchitis (bronchitis), haemoglobin (hemoglobin), anaemia (anemia), diagnosis,Chirurgicam operationem (surgical operation), tabuletta (tablet),hypertonia (high blood pressure),hypotensia (decreased tone), dermatitis (dermatitis), cardiography (cardiograph), myocardium (myocardium), orthopaedic (orthopaedics) ,orthodontia (orthodontics), prophylasso (prevention), therapia (therapy),coma, comatis -coma (deep depression of the central nervous system with complete loss of consciousness),erythēma -erythema (limited hyperemia / redness / of the skin),eczēma -eczema (skin rash),emphysēma -emphysema (swelling of an organ or tissue),empyēma -empyema (accumulation of pus in the cavity),oedema- edema (swelling),trauma-injury, dyspnoë -dyspnea,phlegmone, es f etc.

There are no people who speak Latin now. One of the main reasons why this language can be called one of the most tenacious "dead" languages is that Latin is today the only active, albeit partially used (not spoken) language. In addition, the popularity of Latin in the modern world is also added by the fact that to this day Latin is used in the Catholic Church. The documentation of the Vatican and the messages of the popes are also issued in this language. In Latin, now, in accordance with the established Western theological tradition, scientists carry out dissertation research and participate in scientific debates. Apparently, there is no other professional activity where human experience has had such an effective impact on the terminology used in medicine. Latin plays a significant role in the training of specialists in the field of pharmacy and medicine. Doctors have to deal with this language every day when studying medical literature, medicines and the names of chemical compounds reflected in the International Nomenclature and reading the names of diseases, primarily in the formulation.

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